

Comparison of different MAX_REJECTION_TIMES

The comparison of the training curves with MAX_REJECTION_TIMES as 6, 24, 48, and 72, based on the trace SDSC-SP2 and scheduling policy SJF. It shows 48 and 72 perform similarly and better than other cases.